

Graphical abstract

RESEARCH HIGHLIGHTS

- Low-cost sensors can enable high density monitoring of air pollutants.
- We review the performance of low-cost sensors for monitoring air pollution.
- Data quality is a major concern for the measurements from low-cost sensors.
- The sensors should be frequently calibrated under final deployment conditions.
- Sensor aging and manufacturing variability should be accounted during measurements.

1 **End-user Perspective of Low-cost Sensors for Outdoor Air Pollution Monitoring**

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17 **ABSTRACT**

18 Low-cost sensor technology can potentially revolutionise the area of air pollution monitoring by
19 providing high-density spatiotemporal pollution data. Such data can be utilised for supplementing
20 traditional pollution monitoring, improving exposure estimates, and raising community
21 awareness about air pollution. However, data quality remains a major concern that hinders the
22 widespread adoption of low-cost sensor technology. Unreliable data may mislead unsuspecting
23 users and potentially lead to alarming consequences such as reporting acceptable air pollutant
24 levels when they are above the limits deemed safe for human health. This article provides
25 scientific guidance to the end-users for effectively deploying low-cost sensors for monitoring air
26 pollution and people’s exposure, while ensuring reasonable data quality. We review the
27 performance characteristics of several low-cost particle and gas monitoring sensors and provide
28 recommendations to end-users for making proper sensor selection by summarizing the
29 capabilities and limitations of such sensors. The challenges, best practices, and future outlook for
30 effectively deploying low-cost sensors, and maintaining data quality is also discussed. For data
31 quality assurance, a two-stage sensor calibration process is recommended, which includes
32 laboratory calibration under controlled conditions by the manufacturer supplemented with routine
33 calibration checks performed by the end-user under final deployment conditions. For large sensor
34 networks where routine calibration checks are impractical, statistical techniques for data quality
35 assurance should be utilised. Further advancements and adoption of sophisticated mathematical
36 and statistical techniques for sensor calibration, fault detection, and data quality assurance can
37 indeed help to realise the promised benefits of a low-cost air pollution sensor network.

38 **KEYWORDS:** Pollution exposure; Human health; Outdoor pollution sensing; Environmental
39 sensing; Real-time exposure

40 **LIST OF ACRONYMS**

41 CV: Coefficient of variation

42 EC: Electrochemical

43 EU: European Union

44 LOD: Limit of detection

45 MOS: Metal-oxide-semiconductor

46 nRMSE: Normalised root mean square error

47 PM: Particulate matter

48 $PM_{2.5}$ = PM less than 2.5 μm in diameter

49 PM_{10} = PM less than 10 μm in diameter

50 R^2 : Coefficient of determination

51 R^2_{adj} : Adjusted coefficient of determination

52 RH: Relative humidity

53 RMSE: Root mean square error

54 SD: Standard deviation

55 SE: Standard error

56 t_{lag} : Time interval between a step change in input concentration and the first observable
57 corresponding change in measurement response

58 t_{rise} : Time interval between initial measurement response and 95% of final response after a step
59 increase in input concentration

60 t_{0-90} : Time interval needed by a sensor to reach 90% of the final stable value

61 t_{90-0} : Time interval needed by a sensor to reach zero concentration

62 t_{90} : Mean of t_{0-90} and t_{90-0}

63 **1. INTRODUCTION**

64 Outdoor air pollution is a major problem in the 21st century, attributing to ~3.7 million deaths

65 globally (WHO 2014). Today, ~92% of the world's population lives in regions where air

66 pollutant levels are higher than the WHO-specified limits (WHO 2016). In addition, air pollution

67 is also responsible for global climate change (Ramanathan and Feng 2009) and environmental

68 problems such as acid rain (Menz and Seip 2004), haze (Li and Zhang 2014; Xu et al., 2013),

69 ozone depletion (Solomon 1999; Solomon et al., 1986), and damage to crop (Avnery et al.,

70 2011a; Avnery et al., 2011b; Van Dingenen et al., 2009). Thus, there is a global drive to tackle
71 this problem (Fenger 2009).

72 Traditionally, air pollution is monitored by measuring concentrations of various pollutants such
73 as carbon monoxide (CO), ozone (O₃), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), and
74 particulate matter (PM) at fixed sites by using accurate and expensive instrumentation (Kumar et
75 al., 2014; Mouzourides et al., 2015; Sharma et al., 2013). Monitoring sites in the EU are
76 determined based on the EU Air Quality Directive 2008/50/EC, which clearly defines the
77 minimum number of fixed monitoring stations for each target pollutant based on the air pollution
78 levels, population, and coverage area. Such sites are generally spread in and around cities and
79 provide temporal concentrations (typically hourly) of different pollutants. Cities in developed
80 countries might contain one official monitoring station covering about 100,000 people as
81 opposed to covering millions of people in cities of developing and highly polluted countries. For
82 example, there are around 300 monitoring sites in the UK (DEFRA 2011) and around 600 in
83 India (CPCB 2017). However, they are insufficient to provide accurate information about the
84 spatial distribution of pollutants or identify pollution hotspots, and even more so for developing
85 countries. Even though pollutant dispersion models can be used to address this issue, their
86 accuracy is rather limited (Holmes and Morawska 2006; Kumar et al., 2011; Kumar et al., 2015;
87 Vardoulakis et al., 2003).

88 Recent advancements in the field of sensors, digital electronics, and wireless communication
89 technology have led to the emergence of a new paradigm for air pollution monitoring (Hagler et
90 al., 2013; Kumar et al., 2015). This paradigm aims to gather high-resolution spatiotemporal air
91 pollution data by using a ubiquitous network of low-cost sensors for monitoring real-time

92 concentrations of different air pollutants, which can be then utilised for a variety of air pollution
93 management tasks such as (i) supplementing conventional air pollution monitoring; (ii)
94 improving the link between pollutant exposure and human health; (iii) emergency response
95 management, hazardous leak detection, and source compliance monitoring; and (iv) increasing
96 community's awareness and engagement towards air quality issues.

97 Though there is no universally agreed definition of a "low-cost" sensor since anything costing
98 less than the instrumentation cost required for demonstrating compliance with the air quality
99 regulations can be termed as low-cost. However, the cost should be as low as possible to achieve
100 the above-mentioned aims of a sensor-based system for monitoring air pollution, so that
101 widespread deployment is commercially feasible. Thus, in this paper, the term low-cost sensor is
102 used either for designating sensors costing only a few 10's of US dollars or for sensing
103 kits/nodes/platforms costing a few 100's of US dollars. The higher cost of sensing kits is
104 expected since they typically include one or more sensors, microprocessor, data-logger, memory
105 card, battery, and display.

106 Several review articles have already addressed this emerging area of sensor-based air quality
107 monitoring (Table 1). A majority of these articles focus on the needs, benefits, challenges, and
108 future directions of a sensor-based pollution monitoring paradigm for different applications
109 (Castell et al., 2013; Kumar et al., 2016a; Kumar et al., 2015; Kumar et al., 2016b; Snyder et al.,
110 2013; White et al., 2012). A few others discuss emerging sensor technologies for monitoring
111 gaseous and/or particulate air pollutants (Aleixandre and Gerbolesb 2012; Bhanarkar et al., 2016;
112 White et al., 2012; Zhou et al., 2015). On-going air quality management campaigns using sensor
113 networks were reviewed in some other articles (Castell et al., 2013; Thompson 2016). However,

114 none of them have comprehensively addressed the crucial aspect of *performance assessment* of
115 low-cost sensors for monitoring different air pollutants vis-à-vis their more expensive
116 counterparts. Jovašević-Stojanović et al. (2015) provided some information about selecting low-
117 cost PM sensors based on their specifications and the monitoring objectives. However, they did
118 not include gaseous sensors, and several new research articles on performance assessment of PM
119 sensors have come up since then. Williams et al. (2014b) provided guidelines regarding sensor
120 selection but these guidelines are open ended and leave it for end-users to carefully review a
121 sensor's performance before purchasing it. Without a proper understanding of the performance
122 characteristics of the available low-cost sensors, the end-users cannot be expected to effectively
123 deploy them for achieving an effective sensor-based management of air pollution (Castell et al.,
124 2016; Jovašević-Stojanović et al., 2015; Judge and Wayland 2014; Lewis and Edwards 2016).
125 Addressing this crucial issue forms the motivation for this review article.

126 We recognise a need for providing scientific guidance to end-users in choosing appropriate low-
127 cost sensors by matching user requirements with sensor performance. Through a comprehensive
128 review of the scientific literature, we assessed the performance of several commercially available
129 low-cost sensors for measuring PM and gaseous pollutants in the outdoor environment, i.e., CO,
130 O₃ and NO₂. We could not review the low-cost sensors for measuring SO₂ due to a dearth of
131 studies on their performance assessment. Additionally, we have provided recommendations for
132 end-users in selecting low-cost sensors for monitoring outdoor air pollutants. Finally, we have
133 outlined the challenges faced by the end-users in deploying low-cost sensors for monitoring air
134 pollution and the future research directions to overcome them.

135 **2. LOW-COST SENSORS FOR MONITORING PARTICULATE MATTER**

136 The light scattering method is used in low-cost PM sensors since the sensors based on this

137 principle are cheap to manufacture, have low power requirements, and quick response times
138 (Wang et al., 2015). In this method, a light source illuminates the particles, and then the scattered
139 light from the particles is measured by a photometer. For particles with diameters greater than
140 $\sim 0.3 \mu\text{m}$, the amount of light scattered is roughly proportional to their mass/number
141 concentration; however, particles smaller than $\sim 0.3 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter do not scatter enough light,
142 and cannot be detected by this method (Koehler and Peters 2015; Thomas and Gebhart 1994).
143 The detectable particles ($>0.3 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter) can be size-segregated by either using an
144 algorithm on the signal obtained from the scattered light (Northcross et al., 2013) or by attaching
145 an impactor/filter at the inlet (Sousan et al., 2016b).

146 **2.1 Specifications and application areas**

147 Low-cost PM sensors are available from several manufacturers, and their specifications are given
148 in Table 2 as claimed by their respective makers. These sensors are roughly palm-sized, weigh a
149 few 10's of grams (or 100's of grams for sensor kits), are battery operable, and cost around \$10–
150 100 (or \$100–500 for the sensor kits). The typical range of measurement extends from a few
151 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to about 100's of $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

152 Some of the sensor models such as the GP2Y1010AU0F, DSM501A, PPD42NS, PPD60PV, and
153 SDS198 (Table 2) cannot distinguish between particle sizes and typically report the concentration
154 of particles with sizes greater than $\sim 0.3 \mu\text{m}$ as a single value for the PM concentration in air.
155 Other sensor models such as the Novafit sensors and Dylos (Table 2) rely on size discrimination
156 by applying signal processing techniques on the photometer's output. However, this technique
157 might result in significant misclassification of particles (Sousan et al., 2016b). We found that the
158 DN7C3CA006 sensor is the only sensor equipped with a virtual impactor that allows only

159 particles $\leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter to pass through the sensing zone, making it suitable for measuring
160 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ (particles less than $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter). It is not known how the Plantower sensors (Table
161 2) perform size discrimination between particles. Thus, to monitor PM_{10} (particles less than 10
162 μm in diameter) or $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ any sensor given in Table 2 would be suitable if an appropriate
163 mechanism for size selection is used. The requirement for a size selection mechanism is not
164 stringent for monitoring PM_{10} since particles $\geq 10 \mu\text{m}$ are difficult to draw in the sensing zone
165 (Koehler and Peters 2015), meaning that the raw sensor output would roughly correspond to the
166 PM_{10} concentration.

167 Many of these sensors have already been used in air quality monitoring studies such as
168 monitoring ambient wood smoke (Olivares and Edwards 2015), risk husk in a rice mill (Zakaria
169 et al., 2014), cigarette smoke in a garage (Rajasegarar et al., 2014), PM levels associated with
170 source activities in homes (Olivares et al., 2012), and urban and rural backgrounds (Steinle et al.,
171 2015). However, there is a huge gap in the scientific literature related to their calibration and
172 performance assessment, which makes it challenging to evaluate the data quality obtained by the
173 different investigations and make comparisons between them. Several PM sensors have not been
174 tested by scientific investigations, making it infeasible to judge their performance (see Table 2).
175 Thus, in the remainder of this paper, we focus only on those low-cost sensors (both for PM and
176 gaseous pollutants) whose performance traits have been tested by at least one scientific
177 investigation. Table S1 gives a summary of investigations focused on testing low-cost PM
178 sensors along with the test conditions and reference instrumentation. Due to the lack of a standard
179 calibration protocol specific for low-cost sensors, studies have used dissimilar calibration
180 methods, including chamber and field testing against a variety of reference instruments, which
181 again makes inter-comparison between them infeasible. Nevertheless, these studies provide

182 crucial information about the performances of low-cost sensors under a variety of operating
183 conditions, as discussed in the following sub-section.

184 **2.2 Performance assessment**

185 Table 3 gives a summary of the performance characteristics of the low-cost PM sensors tested by
186 scientific studies; including their comparisons with reference measurements; repeatability and
187 reproducibility characteristics, limit of detection (LOD); and dependence on particle composition,
188 size, humidity, and temperature. These individual performance criteria are discussed in the
189 subsequent text.

190 *2.2.1 Comparisons with reference measurements*

191 All the investigations summarised in Table S1 compared the measurements from the low-cost PM
192 sensors with relevant high-cost reference instruments. Figure 1 shows the range of values for the
193 coefficient of determination (R^2) between the low-cost PM sensors and the high-cost reference
194 instruments obtained by using a simple linear function from the different investigations. Figure 1
195 also shows that a simple linear function is generally adequate to calibrate the sensor response
196 with the reference measurements, yielding moderate to high R^2 values. However, a few
197 investigations have reported that the sensor response begins to saturate at high particle
198 concentrations (higher than 50–100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and that higher order polynomial or exponential
199 functions are needed to capture this behaviour (Austin et al., 2015; Johnson et al., 2016; Kelly et
200 al., 2017; Manikonda et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2015). Thus, it is necessary to select the
201 appropriate response function for a particular sensor by calibrating it under the full range of
202 expected PM concentrations.

203 Figure 1 also suggests that the sensors typically performed better (with high R^2 values) under
204 laboratory conditions compared with field conditions. This performance deterioration in real-
205 world conditions is attributed to the changing conditions of particle compositions, sizes, and
206 environmental factors, which can drastically impact a sensor's response as discussed below.
207 Thus, on-site calibration of low-cost PM sensors is crucial, and laboratory calibrated sensors
208 should not be directly used for real-world measurements. Furthermore, the sensors should be
209 calibrated individually since even the sensors of the same type can give different outputs even
210 under identical conditions (Austin et al., 2015; Olivares et al., 2012; Sousan et al., 2016b; Wang
211 et al., 2015).

212 ***2.2.2 Repeatability, reproducibility, stability, and limit of detection***

213 Repeatability and reproducibility are defined as the closeness between successive measurements
214 of the same measurand carried out under identical and non-identical conditions of measurement,
215 respectively (Taylor and Kuyatt 1994). Thus, we use the terms sensor repeatability to denote the
216 dispersion between consecutive measurements obtained from a given sensor, whereas
217 reproducibility is used for designating dispersion between measurements obtained by using
218 different sensors of the same model.

219 Repeatability is very difficult to measure for PM sensors due to difficulty in maintaining constant
220 particle concentrations. Wang et al. (2015) reported repeatability characteristics for three
221 different low-cost PM sensors, as measured by the coefficient of variation (CV), to lie between 2
222 and 28% (Table 3). The repeatability deteriorated at low PM concentrations, and all the sensors
223 had CV in the 23–26% range at $\sim 50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ PM concentration (Wang et al., 2015).

224 Regarding reproducibility, several investigations have pointed out that the sensors need to be
225 calibrated individually, illustrating poor reproducibility for the raw sensor outputs. However,
226 after calibration, their reproducibility characteristics get improved (Sousan et al., 2016b). To
227 quantify reproducibility, a few investigations reported CV values ranging from 0.9–16% as
228 given in Table 3 (Sousan et al., 2016a; 2016b), while some others reported the R^2 values ($R^2 =$
229 0.25 to 1.0 in Table 3) between sensors (Holstius et al., 2014; Jiao et al., 2016; Kelly et al., 2017).
230 Manikonda et al. (2016) used the normalised root mean square error (nRMSE) value to quantify
231 sensor reproducibility, and found that the reproducibility was much higher when the sensors were
232 exposed to cigarette smoke (nRMSE = 2.6–22.3%) as compared to Arizona test dust (nRMSE =
233 46.1–118.2%). Sensor reproducibility could get deteriorated due to the accumulation of particles
234 in the sensing zone, which seems more pronounced when the sensors were exposed to larger
235 sized particles (Arizona test dust) as compared to smaller particles (cigarette smoke).

236 We define stability as a sensor's capability to maintain its performance characteristics over a
237 sufficiently long duration (at least a few months). This is a crucial performance trait if low-cost
238 sensors are to be deployed for long-term monitoring. However, only Jiao et al. (2016) have
239 conducted measurements with low-cost PM sensors for a sufficiently long period (2–6 months).
240 They reported an improvement in the adjusted- R^2 (R^2_{adj}) value from 0.45 to 0.56 for a sensor
241 when “days of use” was added as a predictor in the regression model used for calibration. Thus, it
242 seems possible that the sensor's response was changing with time due to sensor aging and/or dust
243 accumulation; however, “days of use” could just have been a confounding variable also. Clearly,
244 more investigations are required to address this crucial issue of sensor stability.

245 Limit of detection (LOD) for a sensor is defined as the lowest concentration of a pollutant that
246 can be significantly differentiated from zero concentration. LOD can be estimated as three times
247 the standard deviation of the sensor output obtained at zero pollutant concentration. It is desirable
248 to have the LOD as low as possible since it determines the lowest detectable concentration. LOD
249 values for the different PM sensors have only been evaluated by a few studies (Table 3) and lie
250 between 1–27 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Figure 2 shows the LOD for the different low-cost PM and gaseous sensors
251 together with the pollutant concentrations (urban and background) typically found in EU
252 countries and their corresponding limits. It is evident that the LOD for all the PM sensors (except
253 GP2Y1010AU0F) is less than the EU specified limits for both $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} and lie in the
254 lower spectrum of the concentration ranges found in EU nations. Note that the high LOD values
255 for the GP2Y1010AU0F sensor reported by Wang et al. (2015) likely to rise since they probably
256 did not account for the large intercept present in the sensor calibration curve while calculating its
257 LOD. Generally, the PM sensors seem suitable for measuring both $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10}
258 concentrations, unless the concentrations are very low ($<10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). However, given that PM_{10}
259 levels are always higher than $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ levels, the sensors would be better suited for monitoring
260 PM_{10} .

261 ***2.2.3 Impact of particle characteristics on sensor output***

262 The impact of particle composition on outputs of the low-cost PM sensors has been studied by a
263 few laboratory investigations (Northcross et al., 2013; Sousan et al., 2016a; Sousan et al., 2016b;
264 Wang et al., 2015). This factor was found to affect the sensor outputs by as much as 30 times for
265 the various sensors (Table 3). One field investigation reported that the output of Dylos sensor was
266 unaffected by the change in aerosol composition from secondary inorganic aerosols to sea-salt
267 dominated aerosols (Steinle et al., 2015). Since the chamber investigations have used aerosols

268 with significantly different compositions ranging from polystyrene latex spheres (Northcross et
269 al., 2013), sugar (Wang et al., 2015), salt (Northcross et al., 2013; Sousan et al., 2016a; Sousan et
270 al., 2016b; Wang et al., 2015), wood-smoke (Northcross et al., 2013), diesel exhaust (Sousan et
271 al., 2016b), welding fumes (Sousan et al., 2016a; Sousan et al., 2016b) to road dust (Sousan et al.,
272 2016a; Sousan et al., 2016b) compared with the field investigations, the high variability in sensor
273 outputs during laboratory testing is reasonable. The difference in particle composition impacts the
274 scattering and absorption of light by the sensors; thus, affecting their outputs. For example,
275 organic materials tend to absorb a higher proportion of incident light as compared to inorganic
276 materials. This means that the optical sensors will report a much higher concentration when
277 measuring organic particles as compared to inorganic particles, even under identical
278 concentrations (Wang et al., 2015).

279 Some investigations have studied the impact of particle size on the outputs of low-cost PM
280 sensors as given in Table 3 (Austin et al., 2015; Han et al., 2016; Sousan et al., 2016a; Sousan et
281 al., 2016b; Wang et al., 2015). The sensor outputs are generally found to increase with the
282 particle size since for the same mass concentration larger particles scatter more light, which
283 results in higher reported concentrations (Wang et al., 2015). For example, Wang et al. (2015)
284 reported that the output of the sensor with 900 nm size particles was as high as 2–24 times when
285 compared to their outputs with 300 nm size particles at similar mass concentrations. All the low-
286 cost PM sensors show similar dependence on particle size except for the OPC-N2, which seems
287 relatively unaffected by particle sizes (Sousan et al., 2016a); however, the reason is unknown.

288 *2.2.4 Impact of environmental factors on sensor output*

289 The impact of environmental factors (relative humidity and temperature) has been assessed by
290 several investigations (Table 3). For example, Wang et al. (2015) used an environmental chamber
291 to study the effect of environmental factors on the performance of three different PM sensors by
292 comparing their outputs under different relative humidity and temperature conditions, while
293 maintaining similar PM mass concentrations. They found that the sensors outputs first increased,
294 and then decreased as the relative humidity was increased from 20% to 90%. The ratios of the
295 sensor outputs at different humidity conditions ranged from 1.5–8.0 (Table 3). However, the
296 impact of temperature on sensor outputs was very less as compared to humidity, with the ratios of
297 the sensor outputs ranging from 1.2–1.6 at different temperatures (5–32°C). The effect of
298 humidity on sensor outputs is attributed to a combination of factors: (i) absorption of radiation by
299 water causing an overestimation of particle concentrations, (ii) unsuitability of the reference
300 instrument used at high humidity conditions, and (iii) probable circuit failure in particle sensors
301 at high relative humidity. Whereas light scattering and absorption are theoretically independent of
302 temperature, which means that temperature variations should not affect an optical sensor's
303 output.

304 Of the several field investigations that have looked into the effects of environmental factors on
305 the outputs from different low-cost PM sensors, almost all have reported that the sensor outputs
306 do not seem to be associated with humidity or temperature (Table 3). Olivares et al. (2012)
307 reported that the baseline response of a PM sensor was linearly proportional to the temperature.
308 However, the same lead author later reported that this linear relationship was probably because
309 the temperature affects the measured particles, and not because it affects the sensor (Olivares and
310 Edwards 2015).

311 Overall, there seems to be a consensus between the field investigations that the low-cost PM
312 sensor outputs are not affected by humidity or temperature variations. However, the laboratory
313 investigation (Wang et al., 2015) discussed previously had a conflicting conclusion about the
314 effect of humidity on sensor outputs. Laboratory investigations are preferred for such
315 assessments since field investigations do not have a control over all the variables that can impact
316 the output of a sensor, and it is not possible to deduce causal relationships. Thus, more laboratory
317 studies are required to address this contradiction.

318 **2.3 Recommendations for end-users**

319 Several low-cost PM sensors are available in the market that measures the concentration of
320 particles based on the light scattering method. This method is suitable only for measuring
321 particles larger than $\sim 0.3 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter since smaller particles do not scatter enough light. To
322 use this technique for measuring $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ or PM_{10} , it should be ensured that the sensor is equipped
323 with an impactor or filter at the air inlet that provides the appropriate cut-off diameter ($2.5 \mu\text{m}$
324 and $10 \mu\text{m}$ for measuring $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} , respectively). This feature is not provided in any of
325 the sensors given in Table 2, except for the DN7C3CA006 sensor that is equipped with a $2.5 \mu\text{m}$
326 virtual impactor. A few sensors (e.g. Dylos) utilise signal processing algorithms to categorise
327 particles between $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} ; however, such algorithms may lead to significant
328 misclassification (Sousan et al., 2016b). Thus, to measure concentrations of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ or PM_{10} , any
329 optical sensor (Table 2) can be used in principle when combined with a suitable size cut-off
330 mechanism.

331 It is also important to note that a few low-cost PM sensors (e.g., GP2Y1010AU0G and
332 PPD42NS) are available as stand-alone sensors, and require integration into a data acquisition

333 and storage system. However, other sensors (e.g., Dylos and Novafitness SDL301) are available
334 as ready-to-use modules with their own data acquisition, storage, and display system. Based on
335 the user's familiarity with these issues, an appropriate choice can be made.

336 A number of investigations have assessed the performance of low-cost PM sensors. However, the
337 lack of a standardised method for performance assessment of low-cost PM sensors makes it
338 difficult to make inter-comparisons between the results obtained from different studies.
339 Nevertheless, the performance characteristics of the different sensors seem to be roughly similar
340 (Table 3). The sensors generally demonstrate R^2 values greater than 0.50 when compared with
341 reference measurements. The CV value, which is generally used to characterise sensor
342 repeatability and reproducibility, is in the 1–28% range. This means that even if the sensors work
343 perfectly, 1–28% errors in PM concentrations can be expected. The LOD ranges from 1–27
344 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and generally lies at the lower spectrum of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} concentration ranges in
345 EU countries. It is also seen that the sensors' outputs are highly dependent on the particle
346 composition and size. Environmental factors such as relative humidity and temperature might
347 also influence PM sensors' response; however, further investigations are required to understand
348 this influence. Sensor stability is another inadequately understood issue.

349 Thus, the end-users should be aware of the above-mentioned characteristics, performance traits,
350 and limitations of the low-cost PM sensors when deploying them. Before performing any PM
351 monitoring task, the sensors should be properly calibrated under conditions as close to the final
352 deployment as possible. Furthermore, since the long-term (more than a week) performance of
353 these low-cost sensors largely remains unknown, frequent calibration is recommended.

354 3. LOW-COST SENSORS FOR MONITORING GASEOUS POLLUTANTS

355 3.1 Specifications and application areas

356 To measure gaseous air pollutants, there are currently two types of low-cost sensors available in
357 the market: (i) metal-oxide-semiconductor (MOS) sensors, and (ii) electrochemical (EC) sensors.

358 The MOS sensors employ a metal oxide that changes its electrical properties (typically
359 resistance) when exposed to the target gas. This change can be easily measured and corresponds
360 to the concentration of the gas (Fine et al., 2010). Such sensors are small in size (a few
361 millimetres), light-weight (a few grams), inexpensive (~\$10), have quick response times, low
362 detection limits and power requirements (~100 mW) (Aleixandre and Gerbolesb 2012; Piedrahita
363 et al., 2014). However, they have a non-linear response curve; and suffer from sensitivity to
364 changes in environmental conditions and interfering gases (Spinellea et al., 2016).

365 The EC sensors are generally operated in an amperometric mode, wherein the electrochemical
366 reactions between the target gas and an electrolyte produce a current dependent on the gaseous
367 concentration (Stetter and Li 2008). The sensors typically consist of three electrodes, termed as
368 working, counter, and reference. The target gas undergoes electrolysis (oxidation or reduction) at
369 the working electrode and generates an electric current, which is balanced by the reaction at the
370 counter electrode. The measured electric current corresponds to the concentration of the gas, and
371 the response is either linear or logarithmic (Aleixandre and Gerbolesb 2012). The reference
372 electrode is typically employed in the sensor to ensure that the working electrode is maintained at
373 the correct operating potential. These sensors are claimed to have lower detection limits, power
374 requirements (~100 μ W), and sensitivity to changes in environmental conditions and interfering

375 gases than MOS sensors, but are also larger (few tens of millimeters in size), and more expensive
376 (~\$100) (Aleixandre and Gerbolesb 2012; Piedrahita et al., 2014).

377 Low-cost gas sensors have been used in several air quality campaigns ranging from background
378 pollutant measurements at rural and urban sites (Jiang et al., 2016; Spinelle et al., 2015b; Sun et
379 al., 2016), measurements of road-side pollution (Mead et al., 2013; Popoola et al., 2016), mobile
380 vehicular measurements (Hu et al., 2011; Suriano et al., 2015), source attribution (Heimann et al.,
381 2015), and personal exposure monitoring (Jiang et al., 2011; Piedrahita et al., 2014). However,
382 their performance characteristics are not well understood, and we found only a few studies
383 focused on their performance assessment (Table S2). Based on those studies, we have evaluated
384 the performance of low-cost sensors for O₃, NO₂, and CO in the following sub-sections.

385 **3.2 Performance assessment of O₃ sensors**

386 We found several MOS O₃ sensors and a few EC O₃ sensors that have been tested in scientific
387 studies. Their key performance characteristics are summarised in Table 4 and discussed below.

388 ***3.2.1 Comparisons with reference measurements***

389 Figure 3 shows the comparisons between the outputs from the low-cost O₃ sensors and reference
390 measurements, as quantified by the R^2 values during laboratory and field testing. Clearly, both
391 EC and MOS sensors perform very well during laboratory tests ($R^2 > 0.90$); however, their
392 performance gets deteriorated under real-world conditions ($R^2 = 0.01-0.94$). This performance
393 deterioration is expected since these low-cost sensors are generally prone to sensitivities to
394 environmental conditions, gaseous co-pollutants, and aging (Spinelle et al., 2015b; 2017).

395 The MOS O₃ sensors have been tested by a few studies under chamber conditions. Williams et al.
396 (2014c) tested three different MOS sensors in an exposure chamber under four different
397 conditions (normal, hot, humid, and cold). They generally found high R^2 values (0.88–0.99).
398 However, it should be noted that the MICS-2611 sensor could not complete the tests under hot
399 (temperature $\geq 50^\circ\text{C}$) and humid (RH $\geq 85\%$) conditions since its response was found unstable
400 under those conditions. Spinellea et al. (2016) tested four MOS O₃ sensors in an exposure
401 chamber, and reported the residual values (reference concentration minus the sensor measured
402 concentration) for those sensors. At O₃ concentrations ranging from 0–110 ppb, the residuals
403 were quite low (2.0–4.2 ppb) for three sensors; however, the residual was as high as 13.3 ppb for
404 the MICS-2610 sensor. Low standard errors (SE = 3–8 ppb) were reported by Williams et al.
405 (2013) while testing the S300 sensor under chamber conditions.

406 Some studies have tested MOS O₃ sensors under real-world conditions. Like the chamber
407 investigations, they have also reported moderate to excellent R^2 values (0.77–0.94); except for
408 Borrego et al. (2016) who reported R^2 as 0.12 for the MICS 2610 sensor, which seems due to
409 sensor malfunctioning. Interestingly, the same sensor model also perform poorly in the chamber
410 investigation by Spinellea et al. (2016) as mentioned in the previous paragraph. Piedrahita et al.
411 (2014) conducted a measurement campaign at an air quality monitoring station, and tested eight
412 identical MOS sensors (MICS 2611), and reported that the median value of the root mean
413 squared error (RMSE) was 6.1 ppb. The S300 sensor has also been evaluated under different
414 outdoor conditions, and reported to have SE values between 5–6 ppb (Bart et al., 2014; Williams
415 et al., 2013). Overall, the laboratory and field testing of the MOS O₃ sensors generally show good
416 comparisons between the sensors and reference measurements.

417 The performances of EC O₃ sensors have been tested by a few investigation (Table 4). Spinelle
418 and co-workers (Spinelle et al., 2015a; Spinelle et al., 2015b) assessed the performances of two
419 different EC sensors under chamber and field conditions. During the chamber study, the R^2 was
420 greater than 0.99 for both the sensors (Spinelle et al., 2015a). However, when those sensors were
421 calibrated under field conditions, the R^2 was 0.02 and 0.84–0.88 for the O3B4 and O3_3E1F
422 sensors, respectively (Spinelle et al., 2015b). Thus, it seems that the O3B4 sensor was faulty, and
423 we don't discuss additional results for this sensor obtained by Spinelle et al. (2015b). To better
424 calibrate the O3_3E1F sensor, they used multiple linear regression models by including the
425 concentration of NO₂ as an additional predictor, which improved the R^2 values (0.85–0.94). The
426 linear models were then tested for 4.5 months of field deployment of the O3_3E1F sensor in the
427 validation phase of the study. During this phase, the sensor performance deteriorated
428 significantly, and the R^2 was between 0.67–0.81 and 0.58–0.82 with the simple and multiple
429 linear regression models, respectively. This indicates that the response curves of the sensors were
430 time variable possibly due to sensor aging and/or dust accumulation. Borrego et al. (2016)
431 reported $R^2 = 0.13–0.70$ during field testing of the O3B4 sensor when it was deployed as a part of
432 three different platforms under identical conditions. The different sensor platforms might use
433 distinct signal processing techniques for converting the raw sensor response to the O₃
434 concentration, which might be the reason for the high variations in the R^2 values.

435 *3.2.2 Repeatability, reproducibility, stability, limit of detection, and response times*

436 The repeatability characteristics of different MOS and EC O₃ sensors have been studied by a few
437 chamber investigations, by quantifying the standard deviations (SD) of their outputs obtained
438 under identical conditions (Table 4). Spinellea et al. (2016) reported good repeatability
439 characteristics for three different MOS sensors at 100 ppb O₃ (SD = 0.2–3.3 ppb); however the
440 SP-61 MOS sensor was found to have poor repeatability (SD = 19.8 ppb) under similar
441 conditions. Williams et al. (2014c) found variable repeatability characteristics (SD = 2.6–46.2
442 ppb) for different MOS sensors depending upon the sensor model, O₃ concentration, humidity,
443 and temperature. However, they did not report the O₃ concentration range under which the
444 different values were obtained, which makes it difficult to judge the relative measurement
445 uncertainties. For the EC O₃ sensors, the SD values range from 0.4–1.9 ppb at 100 ppb O₃ (Table
446 4). Overall, it appears that both MOS and EC O₃ sensors have similar repeatability traits, and the
447 measurement uncertainty would typically be less than 5% at 100 ppb O₃ concentration if the
448 sensors worked perfectly.

449 The reproducibility of MOS O₃ sensors has been quantified by a few studies (Moltchanov et al.,
450 2015; Piedrahita et al., 2014) through the computation of R^2 between the responses of several
451 identical sensors under similar conditions. Moltchanov et al. (2015) reported high reproducibility
452 between sensors ($R^2 = 0.85–0.98$), whereas Piedrahita et al. (2014) reported variable
453 reproducibility ($R^2 = 0.21–0.98$). We did not find studies that reported reproducibility
454 characteristics for the EC O₃ sensors.

455 The stability of four different MOS sensors and two different EC sensors was studied by Spinella
456 and co-workers under laboratory conditions (Spinelle et al., 2015a; Spinellea et al., 2016). They

457 reported that the sensor drifts ranged from -0.009 to 0.081 ppb O_3 /day and 0.016 to 0.142 ppb
458 O_3 /day for the MOS and EC sensors, respectively, during their six months testing. This translates
459 to -2 to 15 ppb and 3 to 26 ppb difference in sensor outputs for the MOS and EC sensors,
460 respectively, in six months. Thus, there does not seem to be a significant difference between the
461 stability characteristics of the MOS and EC O_3 sensor. However, the different models of the
462 EC/MOS sensors exhibit different drifts values, meaning that the sensor manufacturing process
463 might be playing a role in their stability.

464 A few field investigations have also reported the stability characteristics of the low-cost O_3
465 sensors. For the O3_3E1F EC sensor, Spinelle et al. (2015b) reported a significant decrease in R^2
466 values between the sensor response and the reference measurements from the calibration phase to
467 the validation phase, indicating poor stability. Moltchanov et al. (2015) reported that the
468 regression coefficients of the calibration curve of SM50 MOS sensor changed with time possibly
469 because of aging and/or dust accumulation in the sensors due to episodic events (e.g., rain and
470 dust storms). However, Jiao et al. (2016) did not find any association between the response of
471 SM50 sensor and the “days of use” during their field campaign, suggesting that episodic dust
472 accumulation might be the causing the response changes reported by Moltchanov et al. (2015).
473 For the S300 MOS sensor, Williams et al. (2013) reported their long-term stability characteristics
474 in monitoring campaigns conducted at several outdoor sites (Table 4). The sensor response was
475 generally stable over several months of operation; however, at a heavily industrial site, significant
476 sensor drift was observed due to dust accumulation at the inlet filter (Williams et al., 2009).
477 Clearly, sensor stability is an important consideration, if long term O_3 measurements are to be
478 conducted.

479 The LOD for different MOS and EC O₃ sensors were reported by a few investigations (Table 4).
480 For the MOS sensors, the LOD values reported by Spinellea et al. (2016) were 0.5–2.3 ppb,
481 which are much lower than the LOD values (5.1–23.4 ppb) reported by Williams et al. (2014c),
482 due to the different methods employed for computing those values by the two investigations. For
483 the EC sensors, the LOD ranges from 1.8–6.8 ppb, as obtained by a method identical to
484 Spinellea et al. (2016). Thus, the LODs for the EC and MOS O₃ sensors seem comparable when
485 same estimation method is used. Furthermore, the LODs are much lower than the typical ambient
486 O₃ concentrations found in EU countries (Figure 2), meaning that the sensors seem suitable for
487 measuring ambient O₃.

488 The response times of four different MOS and two different EC O₃ sensors were reported by
489 Spinellea and co-workers (Spinelle et al., 2015a; Spinellea et al., 2016). They reported the t_{90}
490 values, which is defined as the mean of t_{0-90} (the time needed by a sensor to reach 90% of the
491 final stable value) and t_{90-0} (the time needed by a sensor to reach zero concentration). The t_{90} was
492 4.4–89 min and 1.4–1.8 min for the different MOS and EC sensors, respectively. Williams et al.
493 (2014c) reported the t_{lag} (time interval between a step change in input concentration and the first
494 observable corresponding change in measurement response) and t_{rise} (time interval between the
495 initial measurement response and 95% of final response after a step increase in input
496 concentration) times for three different MOS sensors. The t_{lag} and t_{rise} were between 1–3 min and
497 2–8 min, respectively (Table 4). Thus, the t_{90} can be roughly calculated to be around 10 minutes
498 (by summing the t_{lag} and t_{rise}) for the different sensors, which is within the range of values
499 reported by Spinellea et al. (2016) for the MOS sensors. Overall, the response times of the MOS
500 O₃ sensors seem to be about 5–10 times that of EC sensors, meaning that EC sensors are
501 preferable if the high temporal resolution is required in O₃ measurements.

502 ***3.2.3 Impact of environmental factors and gaseous cross-sensitivities on sensor output***

503 Environmental factors such as temperature and relative humidity have been found to significantly
504 affect the outputs from MOS and EC O₃ sensors (Table 4). During the chamber testing by
505 Spinellea et al. (2016), responses of the four different MOS sensors were found to decrease by
506 0.7–3.86 ppb O₃ per 1°C increase at temperatures ranging from 12 to 32 °C. In those chamber
507 tests, relative humidity was also found to impact the response of the MOS sensors with the
508 change being –0.65 to 0.84 ppb O₃ per percentage point increase in relative humidity. However,
509 during field testing negligible/little association has been observed between the responses from
510 three different MOS sensors and temperature or humidity (Bart et al., 2014; Jiao et al., 2016; Lin
511 et al., 2015).

512 Environmental factors were found to affect outputs of EC O₃ sensors with the responses of
513 different sensors changing by –0.022 to 1.28 ppb O₃ per percentage point increase in relative
514 humidity and by 0 to 1.3 ppb O₃ per 1°C increase in temperature under laboratory testing (Lewis
515 et al., 2016; Spinelle et al., 2015a). However, Spinelle et al. (2015a) did not find any influence of
516 humidity or temperature on the response of EC sensors during their field campaign. The
517 differences between field and chamber measurements are attributed to the inability of field
518 measurements in isolating the effect of a particular factor (such as temperature) on the sensor's
519 response from other confounding factors (e.g., gaseous interferences and sensor aging).

520 Gaseous cross-sensitivity refers to the false response obtained from a sensor because of its
521 sensitivity to gaseous co-pollutants that commonly exist with the target pollutant. We found a
522 few chamber investigations that reported the cross-sensitivities to CO, CO₂, NO, NO₂, SO₂, and
523 NH₃ for different MOS and EC O₃ sensors (Table 4). From the table, it is clear that NO₂

524 interference is a big problem for the EC sensors since the sensor response increases by 0.76–1.0
525 ppb of O₃ per 1 ppb of NO₂.

526 The other cross-sensitivities seem negligible at first glance. However, to fully understand their
527 impact on a sensor's response, we should know the concentration of the co-pollutant gas since the
528 sensor response is a product of the gaseous cross-sensitivity with its corresponding concentration.
529 Thus, we estimated the change in sensor response by multiplying the gaseous cross-sensitivities
530 with their corresponding ambient concentrations. For CO, NO₂, and SO₂ concentrations, we used
531 the EU specified limits; we used a representative value for background urban sites for CO₂ (400
532 ppb), NO (15 ppb), and NH₃ (30 ppb). The estimated changes in MOS sensor outputs were very
533 low (–2.4 ppb to 2.0 ppb) for interferences by CO₂, NO, NO₂, and NH₃. However, CO
534 interference caused a significant change in the MOS sensor outputs (–6.8 ppb to 20 ppb),
535 meaning that cross-sensitivity to CO could be important for such sensors. For EC sensors, the
536 estimated changes in outputs were low for interferences by CO, CO₂, NO, NH₃, and SO₂ (–3.77
537 ppb to 0.048 ppb); however, NO₂ interference causes a significant increase in sensor outputs (16–
538 21 ppb). We also found a few field investigation that reported the negligible influence of gaseous
539 cross-sensitivities on a MOS O₃ sensor under urban ambient concentrations (Bart et al., 2014; Lin
540 et al., 2015). However, under such conditions several co-pollutants will be present, meaning that
541 the overall sensor cross-sensitivity will a combination of the individual cross-sensitivities. If the
542 individual cross-sensitivities cancel each other, the sensor will appear to suffer from no cross-
543 sensitivities problems. Thus, we recommended that the sensor manufacturer/user should first
544 evaluate its cross-sensitivity coefficients (to anticipated levels of co-pollutants) under laboratory
545 conditions, and then perform field calibration under the conditions of actual deployment.

546 3.3 Performance assessment of NO₂ sensors

547 We found that three MOS and five EC NO₂ sensors have been tested by scientific studies. Their
548 performance traits are summarised in Table S3 and discussed below.

549 3.3.1 Comparisons with reference measurements

550 Figure 4 shows the R^2 values between the measurements from the MOS and EC NO₂ sensors and
551 reference instrumentation under laboratory and field conditions. Figure 4 is similar to Figure 3,
552 and the low-cost NO₂ sensors show excellent performance under laboratory conditions. However,
553 their performance gets significantly deteriorated under real-world conditions due to similar
554 reasons as discussed in the case of O₃ sensors. Furthermore, there is considerable variation in R^2
555 values, reported by the different field investigations. For example, the two studies that used MOS
556 NO₂ sensors have conflicting results. Jiao et al. (2016) obtained extremely poor performance (R^2
557 <0.1 between the sensor outputs and the reference measurements) from the MICS-2710 sensor,
558 which was a part of the Air Quality Egg platform. Conversely, Piedrahita et al. (2014) reported
559 reasonable measurement errors (RMSE = 6.9–9.5 ppb) with the same sensor by using a multiple
560 linear regression model for calibration that accounted for temperature and humidity effects on the
561 sensor's response.

562 Of the studies that tested EC NO₂ sensors, a few have reported $R^2 \approx 0.90$ between the sensor
563 response and the reference measurements after applying correction algorithms for interference by
564 O₃ or humidity (Lin et al., 2015; Mead et al., 2013; Sun et al., 2016). Duvall et al. (2016)
565 reported $R^2 = 0.01$ for the CairClip NO₂ sensor; however, the poor sensor performance was
566 attributed to low NO₂ concentrations (5.5 ppb hourly averaged value). Castell et al. (2016) tested
567 24 EC NO₂ sensors as part of the AQMesh platform and reported $R^2 = 0.04–0.52$ during a

568 collocation campaign at a reference station. Their results clearly show that even for identical
569 sensor and platform, drastically different results can be obtained, calling for careful quality
570 control in the manufacturing process for both sensors and platforms.

571 We found a few field investigations that have simultaneously tested MOS and EC NO₂ sensors.
572 The investigation by Borrego et al. (2016) tested one MOS sensor and two EC sensors as part of
573 six different sensor platforms. The MOS sensor performed poorly with $R^2 < 0.1$ between the
574 sensor and the reference measurements, whereas the performance of EC sensors was variable
575 with $R^2 = 0.06\text{--}0.89$ depending on the sensor and platform models. Spinelle et al. (2015b)
576 performed a long-term assessment of two MOS and three EC NO₂ sensors. They reported low R^2
577 for the MOS (0.20–0.21) and EC sensors (0.00–0.46), by using a linear regression model for
578 calibration. However, the R^2 could be considerably improved ($R^2 = 0.52\text{--}0.79$ and $R^2 = 0.35\text{--}0.77$
579 for the MOS and EC sensors, respectively) by using multiple linear regression models with
580 additional predictors such as the concentrations of co-pollutants, humidity, and temperature.
581 Those models were then tested for 4.5 months during the validation period. It was found that the
582 performances of both the simple and multiple linear regression models were very poor during the
583 validation period with $R^2 < 0.2$ for all the sensors probably due to sensor aging.

584 From the above discussion, we conclude that the best performance under real-world conditions
585 has been achieved by performing on-site calibration of the sensors and accounting for the
586 different factors that affect their outputs, rather than relying on manufacturer's calibration. This is
587 because the calibration conditions used by the manufacturer might be drastically different from
588 the actual deployment conditions. Furthermore, sensor aging and manufacturing variability also

589 stand out as important factors that need to be accounted for when conducting measurements using
590 low-cost NO₂ sensors.

591 ***3.3.2 Repeatability, reproducibility, stability, limit of detection, and response times***

592 The repeatability characteristics of different MOS and EC NO₂ sensors have been studied by only
593 a few investigations (Table S3). The SD of repeated measurements ranged from 1.2–7.5 and 4.6–
594 23.3 for MOS and EC NO₂ sensors, respectively, as reported by Williams et al. (2014c) under
595 different chamber conditions. However, they have not reported the NO₂ concentration at which
596 the measurements were conducted, meaning the relative errors cannot be estimated. Spinelle et al.
597 (2015a) and Castell et al. (2016) have reported SD ranging from 0.8–2.9 for different EC NO₂
598 sensors at 100 ppb NO₂ concentration, meaning that 1–3% measurement error can be expected
599 even under ideal measurement conditions.

600 Regarding the reproducibility of the low-cost NO₂ sensor outputs, we noted in the previous sub-
601 section that the R^2 values ranged from 0.04–0.52, when 24 identical NO₂-B4 EC sensors were
602 tested as part of the AQMesh platform by Castell et al. (2016). This demonstrates poor
603 reproducibility characteristics of this sensor platform. However, Mead et al. (2013) found good
604 reproducibility between two pairs of identical NO₂-A1 EC sensors ($R^2 = 0.94–0.95$). Similarly,
605 Piedrahita et al. (2014) also reported good reproducibility ($R^2 = 0.88–0.98$) between
606 measurements from eight identical MICS-2710 MOS sensors. Overall, we found insufficient
607 investigations on sensor reproducibility, and further studies are required to better understand this
608 issue.

609 Sensor *stability* is a concern for low-cost NO₂ sensors, as demonstrated by Spinelle et al. (2015b)
610 for both EC and MOS sensors, and discussed in the previous sub-section. The sensor drifts for

611 EC NO₂ sensors are reported to be between -0.497 to -0.065 ppb/day (Table S3). This would
612 cause a significant decrease in the reported NO₂ concentration (by 12–89 ppb) for a six-month
613 monitoring campaign. Clearly, this effect needs to be considered when conducting long-term
614 campaigns with EC NO₂ sensors.

615 The LOD for the different MOS and EC sensors are plotted in Figure 2 along with the typical
616 NO₂ concentration in EU countries and its corresponding EU specified limit. Almost all the LOD
617 values lie above the minimum measured concentrations, showing that the sensors should not be
618 used in places with very low concentrations of NO₂ (<10 ppb or <20 µg/m³). From the Figure 2,
619 it also appears that the LOD for the MOS sensors is higher than that for the EC sensors.
620 However, the LOD values for the MOS sensors have only been reported by Williams et al.
621 (2014c), who used a different method for estimating LOD as compared to that used by other
622 investigations, thereby reporting much higher values. This is also the reason for the outlier
623 present in EC sensors: NO2-A1 with LOD equals 12–29.4 ppb.

624 The sensor response times for the different MOS and EC NO₂ sensors are also given in Table S3.
625 For the MOS sensors, we can approximate t₉₀ (as the sum of t_{lag} and t_{rise}) to vary between 6 and
626 34 min. For the NO2-A1 EC sensor, the t₉₀ is estimated as 9–19 min. For the other EC sensors,
627 the t₉₀ equals 1.3–1.6 min, except the abnormally high value for the CairPol CairClip sensor (t₉₀ =
628 38.42 min) possibly due to the presence of an O₃ filter and/or a humidity buffer in that sensor.
629 The inter-comparison between the MOS and EC sensors is not feasible due to limited
630 investigations that have studied this sensor trait.

631 *3.3.3 Impact of environmental factors and gaseous cross-sensitivities on sensor output*

632 As discussed above, some field investigations have reported improvements in R^2 values between
633 sensor outputs and reference measurements, if factors such as humidity, temperature, and gaseous
634 co-pollutants are included in the calibration equation. However, there are also others that show
635 insignificant improvements in R^2 , when those factors are included in the calibration equations
636 (Table S3). As previously mentioned, field investigations are unreliable to draw such
637 conclusions, and chamber investigations are preferred.

638 The effects of environmental factors on EC NO₂ sensor outputs have been reported by a few
639 chamber investigations; however, no such investigations were found for the MOS sensors.
640 Spinelle et al. (2015a) found that the sensor response increased by 0.093–0.47 ppb of NO₂ per °C
641 increase in temperature from 12–32 °C for three different EC sensors. However, Sun et al. (2016)
642 did not detect any influence of temperature (15–21°C) on the NO₂-B4 sensor's response. Their
643 temperature range is only 6°C, and we can estimate an increase in the sensor output by only 2.8
644 ppb based on 0.47 ppb NO₂ per °C, reported by Spinelle et al. (2015a), which was probably left
645 undetected by Sun et al. (2016). The impact of humidity on EC sensor outputs was reported to be
646 between –0.057 to 0.13 ppb of NO₂ per % RH increase in humidity (40–80% RH) for three
647 different sensors by Spinelle et al. (2015a). Sun et al. (2016) also found that humidity ranging
648 from 40–70% RH increased the sensor output for the NO₂-B4 sensor; however, Lewis et al.
649 (2016) did not observe any influence of humidity for the same sensor model. Overall, we find
650 conflicting results regarding the effects of humidity and temperature on the response of low-cost
651 NO₂ sensors, which might be arising due to differences in sensor models or manufacturing
652 variations between same sensor types.

653 For the gaseous cross-sensitivities, both field and laboratory studies report that the responses
654 from MOS and EC NO₂ sensors are predominantly affected by O₃ concentration (about 1.0–1.5
655 ppb NO₂ reported by the sensor per ppb of O₃), unless the sensors are equipped with O₃ filters
656 (Table S3). Williams et al. (2014c) reported the cross-sensitivity to SO₂ for two different MOS
657 and one EC sensor; however, the SO₂ concentration in their study was very high (>200 ppb), and
658 unlikely to be found in the outdoor environment. For the other gaseous co-pollutants, cross-
659 sensitivity data is only available for EC NO₂ sensors. We computed the estimated change in
660 sensor response due to those cross-sensitivities by using the procedure described in the section on
661 gaseous cross-sensitivities for ozone. The outputs from EC sensors were estimated to change by
662 –3.3 to 1.3 ppb NO₂ due to cross-sensitivities to CO, CO₂, NO, NH₃, and SO₂. Thus, it seems that
663 these gaseous interferences can be neglected for EC NO₂ sensors.

664 **3.4 Performance assessment of CO sensors**

665 We found that only two MOS CO sensors have been tested by the scientific community. The
666 MICS-5525 CO sensor was tested by two investigations, and both reported poor comparisons
667 between the sensor output and reference measurements (Table S4). Piedrahita et al. (2014) also
668 reported that the MICS-5525 sensor's response decreased linearly when the temperature was
669 increased from 19°C to 40°C during chamber testing. The MICS-5525 sensor's reproducibility
670 was moderate with R^2 between 0.38 to 0.60 (Piedrahita et al., 2014). Another MOS sensor (model
671 MICS-4514) was tested by Spinelle et al. (2017) under field conditions. They reported good
672 agreement ($R^2 = 0.76$ – 0.78) between sensor response and reference measurements when it was
673 calibrated by using simple or multiple linear regression models. However, the same models
674 performed poorly during the 4.5 months validation phase ($R^2 < 0.1$). Like low-cost O₃ and NO₂

675 sensors, it seems that aging is also an important factor for MOS CO sensors, and should be
676 accounted for before making long-term measurements.

677 Three different EC CO sensors have been tested in both chamber and field conditions. In
678 chamber conditions, there is an excellent agreement between the sensor output and reference
679 measurements with $R^2 > 0.99$ (Castell et al., 2016; Mead et al., 2013; Sun et al., 2016). However,
680 the field investigations report significant deterioration and variations in sensor performances
681 (Figure 5). Two field studies reported moderate to excellent R^2 values (0.53–0.97) for the CO-B4
682 sensor (Borrego et al., 2016; Sun et al., 2016). However, two other field studies have reported
683 poor R^2 values (0.17–0.45) for the CO-B4 and TGS-5042 sensors, when calibrating them with
684 reference measurements (Castell et al., 2016; Spinelle et al., 2017). The differences in sensor
685 performances could be attributed to the differences in testing conditions and methods. Note that
686 sensor aging is also important for EC CO sensors since the sensor calibration curve can change
687 significantly over time (Castell et al., 2016; Spinelle et al., 2017).

688 Figure 2 shows the LOD values for the EC CO sensors (LOD = 4–21 ppb from Table S4), which
689 lie well below the typical concentration range of CO in EU countries, meaning that these sensors
690 seem suitable for measuring ambient CO. Mead et al. (2013) reported high sensor-to-sensor
691 reproducibility for the CO-AF sensor ($R^2 = 0.86–0.95$). Sun et al. (2016) reported that the CO-B4
692 sensor was unaffected by humidity and temperature changes during chamber testing. Lewis et al.
693 (2016) reported that the CO-B4 sensor's response will increase by 0.532 ppb CO per percentage
694 point increase in humidity, meaning that the maximum variation in output would be 53.2 ppb
695 (when RH changes from 0 to 100%), which is quite low compared to typical CO concentrations
696 in Europe. Popoola et al. (2016) found that the CO-AF sensor's baseline response was slightly

697 affected by temperature during chamber tests. Thus, it seems that humidity and temperature
698 influences might not be important for EC CO sensors. We computed that the cross-sensitivities to
699 NO₂, O₃, NO, CO₂, and SO₂ would only change the response of the CO-B4 sensor by -1.7 to 1.8
700 ppb from the data given by Lewis et al. (2016) by following the procedure discussed previously.
701 The other investigations (Table S4) also show that the response from EC CO sensors does not
702 seem influenced by gaseous co-pollutants.

703 **3.5 Recommendations for end-users**

704 Two types of low-cost sensors are available in the market for measuring gaseous air pollutants:
705 EC sensors and MOS sensors. From the above discussion, we find that both the sensor types
706 seem to share many performance traits; however, a few significant differences also exist (Table
707 S5). MOS sensors are typically cheaper than EC sensors; however, they also consume much
708 higher power. For O₃ measurements, MOS sensors are preferable over EC sensors since they
709 seem to provide better agreement with reference measurements, and do not suffer from a
710 significant cross-sensitivity to NO₂. However, note that the EC O₃ sensors seem to have a faster
711 response time, meaning they can achieve higher temporal resolution. For NO₂ and CO
712 measurements, both sensor types seem to provide similar levels of comparisons with reference
713 measurements. However, we did not find enough studies that compared the two sensor types for
714 other performance characteristics. Thus, recommending a particular sensor type is not feasible at
715 this stage for NO₂ and CO measurements.

716 Like the low-cost PM sensors, the gaseous sensors are also available as stand-alone sensors or
717 sensor kits such as AQMesh and Air Quality Egg, and an appropriate choice can be made
718 depending on the end user's expertise in data-handling tasks. Note that a few sensor kits (such as

719 AQMesh) have a proprietary data processing algorithm, and caution must be exercised while
720 using them since they have not been calibrated and tested for the end user's test conditions. Thus,
721 to judge the data quality obtained from such kits, it is essential to compare their outputs with the
722 corresponding reference measurements under deployment conditions. For the stand-alone sensors
723 and user-calibrated sensor kits, it is recommended to calibrate them under conditions as close to
724 final deployment as possible. Furthermore, frequent calibration is recommended depending on
725 the sensor's stability.

726 **4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE OUTLOOK**

727 The most important hindrance in deploying low-cost sensors at a large scale is regarding quality
728 control of the data. While many scientific studies have utilised low-cost PM and gaseous sensors
729 in a variety of air pollution monitoring activities, only a few have reported sensor performance
730 characteristics and the associated data quality. To further exacerbate the matter, performance
731 assessments have been done by using different experimental setups, reference equipment, and
732 environmental conditions, making it extremely difficult to make inter-comparisons between them
733 and draw generalised conclusions regarding the data quality. Thus, to deploy a large-scale sensor
734 network and meaningfully use the plethora of data generated, it is imperative to formulate
735 standard guidelines for assessing the short and long-term performance of low-cost sensors, which
736 can be used by all. The onus should ideally be on sensor manufacturers to provide the end-user
737 with information about the data quality expected from a sensor since the manufacturers are best
738 positioned to ensure standardisation of the sensor manufacturing and calibration process.

739 Improper sensor calibration seems to be another issue plaguing the data quality. The sensor
740 response is largely impacted by environmental conditions, particle characteristics (for PM
741 sensors), and gaseous cross-sensitivities (for gas sensors). Thus, calibration methods that don't

742 include these factors are bound to produce erroneous data. The sensor manufacturer should
743 ideally provide a calibration equation by using laboratory testing and identify the major factors
744 that affect their sensor's response. The calibration curve can then be improved by the end-user
745 through testing the sensor under actual conditions of deployment (Williams et al., 2013).
746 Advanced calibration techniques such as neural networks could also be considered since they
747 might be more effective than regression modelling (De Vito et al., 2008; De Vito et al., 2009; De
748 Vito et al., 2015; Esposito et al., 2016; Spinelle et al., 2015b; 2017).

749 In the case of large sensor networks that might be used for making high-resolution spatiotemporal
750 air pollution maps, frequent in-situ calibration might not be practically possible. In such
751 scenarios, advanced statistical techniques for sensor fault detection and data quality verification
752 could be utilised. These include using data consistency checks (Bart et al., 2014), principal
753 components analysis (Harkat et al., 2006; Harkat et al., 2005), network correlations (Alavi-
754 Shoshtari et al., 2013), and algorithm-based mobile quality checks (Hasenfratz et al., 2012;
755 Talampas and Low 2012), some of which have been successfully exploited for managing large-
756 scale ozone sensor networks (Bart et al., 2014; Miskell et al., 2016; Weissert et al., 2017).

757 Once the data obtained from low-cost sensors has met the expected quality criteria (such as the
758 ones specified in the EU Air Quality Directive 2008/50/EC or a user-specified criteria), it can be
759 utilised for its intended purpose. Currently, the sensors are unsuitable for indicative monitoring
760 purpose in EU since they generally cannot meet the data quality objectives as specified in the
761 2008/50/EC directive (Castell et al., 2016; Spinelle et al., 2015b; 2017). The sensors seem to
762 perform better at high pollutant concentrations (Castell et al., 2016), which could present an

763 enhanced opportunity for using such sensors in highly polluted areas (developing countries);
764 however, more studies are required to test the sensors under such conditions.

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1044 Figure 1. Comparisons of the low-cost PM sensors with the reference instruments under
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1046 the bars denote the range of R^2 , as obtained in the studies referred by the alphabets on y-axis
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1048 Figure 2. Limit of detection (LOD values as presented in Tables 3–4 and S3–S4) of low-cost
1049 pollutant sensors along with the typical pollutant concentrations found in EU as well as the
1050 corresponding EU specified reference values (yearly averaged limit for $PM_{2.5}$ and NO_2 , daily
1051 averaged limit for PM_{10} , maximum daily 8-hour averaged target for O_3 , and maximum daily 8-
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1053 maximum values of the annual mean concentrations reported by each EU member state
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1059 Figure 3. Comparisons of the low-cost ozone sensors with the reference instruments under
1060 laboratory and field conditions based on the R^2 (coefficient of determination) values. Note that
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1066 obtained by the different studies given in Table S3.

1067 Figure 5. Comparisons of the low-cost carbon monoxide sensors with the reference instruments
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1069 that the y-axis refers to the different sensor models and the bars denote the range of R^2 , as
1070 obtained by the different studies given in Table S4.

Table 1: Summary of review articles focused on the applications of low-cost sensors for monitoring air pollution.

Author (year)	Study Focus
Aleixandre and Gerbolesb (2012)	Reviewed available commercial sensors for gaseous pollutants and compared their detection ranges with those specified in the European Directive on air quality 2008/50/EC.
White et al., (2012)	Highlighted the synergistic opportunities available between the sensor and wireless communication technologies for reducing human exposure to air pollutants.
Castell et al., (2013)	Reviewed potential application areas of sensor technologies for air quality management. The article also provided a critical analysis of commercially available sensors for gas measurements and emphasised the need for performance assessment of emerging sensor technologies under real-world conditions. Finally, the article summarised 24 different air quality management campaigns based on emerging sensor technologies.
Snyder et al., (2013)	Discussed the changing paradigm of air pollution monitoring due to the emergence of portable air quality sensors. The paper also illustrates a few application areas for such sensors in managing air quality issues together with key challenges and possible solutions.
Jovašević-Stojanović et al., (2015)	Assessed low-cost sensors for monitoring PM, including their specifications and general performance characteristics. They also reported measurements and modelling results to show validation methodology of a particular low-cost PM sensors.
Koehler and Peters (2015)	Reviewed personal exposure assessment to particulate air pollution by using novel sensors developed over last 5–10 years. They also discussed new metrics (that go beyond traditional mass measurements) for evaluating the relationship between particulate matter and its health impacts.
Kumar et al., (2015)	Reviewed the emergence of low-cost sensing technologies for managing air pollution in cities with respect to its need, state-of-the-art, opportunities, challenges, and future directions.
Zhou et al., (2015)	Reviewed state of the art and future perspectives for different types of chemosensors for monitoring gases involved in environmental exhausts (CO ₂ , SO ₂ , NO _x , VOCs), biological signalling (H ₂ S, NO, O ₂), and toxic use (nerve gases, sulphur mustard).
Bhanarkar et al., (2016)	Reviewed the issues and challenges in the design and deployment of wireless sensor nodes for outdoor air pollution monitoring.
Kumar et al., (2016a)	Focused on solving the typical problem of deteriorating indoor air quality (IAQ) in building management programs aimed at conserving energy by proposing to use real-time sensing.
Kumar et al., (2016b)	Highlighted the needs, benefits, challenges, and future outlook of monitoring indoor air quality (IAQ) using real-time sensors. The review also critically analysed the currently available sensor technologies available for monitoring different types of gaseous and particulate air pollutants.
Thompson (2016)	Reviewed current and emerging areas of analytical chemistry and sensor technology suitable for the development of a low-cost sensing platform for monitoring air quality together with a summary of recent crowd-sourced sensing efforts.

1074 *Table 2 Specifications of the different PM sensors as given by their respective manufacturers.*

Model	Size (mm)	Weight (g)	Power supply	Maximum current consumption (mA)	Cost (US \$)	Detectable particle size	Concentration range of measurement	Performance tested in scientific literature
Sharp GP2Y1010AU0F	46×30×18	15	5 V DC	20	~10	Greater than 0.5µm	0–600 µg/m ³	Yes
Sharp DN7C3CA006	50×44×20	52	5 V DC	180	~20	0.5–2.5µm	25–500 µg/m ³	Yes
Samyoung DSM501A	59×45×20	25	5 V DC	90	~15	Greater than 1.0 µm	0–1400 µg/m ³	Yes
Shinyei PPD42NS	59×45×22	24	5 V DC	90	~15	Greater than 1.0 µm	0–28 particles/cm ³	Yes
Shinyei PPD60PV	88×60×20	36	5 V DC	NA	~250	Greater than 0.5 µm	0–70 particles/cm ³	Yes
Dylos DC 1100 Pro	178×114×76	544	110 V AC	NA	~300	0.5–2.5 µm and 0.5–10 µm in two size bins	0–106 particles/cm ³	Yes
Dylos DC 1700	178×114×76	544	110 V AC or battery	NA	~400	0.5–2.5 µm and 0.5–10 µm in two size bins	0–106 particles/cm ³	Yes
Plantower PMS 1003	65×42×23	NA	5 V DC	120	~20	0.3–1.0 µm, 1.0–2.5 µm, and 2.5–10 µm in three size bins	0–500 µg/m ³	Yes
Plantower PMS 3003	65×42×23	NA	5 V DC	120	~20	0.3–1.0 µm, 1.0–2.5 µm, and 2.5–10 µm in three size bins	NA	Yes
Novafitness SDS011	71×70×23	NA	5V DC	80	~35	0.3–2.5 µm and 0.3–10 µm in two size bins	0–1000 µg/m ³	No
Novafitness SDS021	42×32×24	NA	5 V DC	70	~35	0.3–2.5 µm and 0.3–10 µm in two size bins	0–1000 µg/m ³	No
Novafitness SDS018	59×45×20	NA	5 V DC	70	~40	0.3–2.5 µm and 0.3–10 µm in two size bins	0–1000 µg/m ³	No
Novafitness SDL607	73×73×20	120	5 V DC	NA	~120	0.3–2.5 µm and 0.3–10 µm in two size bins	0–1000 µg/m ³	No
Novafitness SDS198	71×70×23	NA	5 V DC	80	~80	1–100 µm	0–20000 µg/m ³	No
Novafitness SDL301	204×100×36	580	5 V DC	NA	~250	0.3–2.5 µm and 0.3–10 µm in two size bins	0–1000 µg/m ³	No
Alphasense OPC-N2	75×64×60	105	5 V DC	175 mA	~500	0.38–17 µm in 16 size bins	0.1–1500,000 µg/m ³	Yes

1075 NA stand for not available.

Table 3: A summary of performance characteristics of low-cost PM sensors

Model	Comparison with reference measurements (R^2)	Repeatability and Reproducibility	Limit of detection ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	Effect of particle composition on sensor output	Effect of particle size on sensor output	Effect of humidity on sensor output	Effect of temperature on sensor output
Alphasense OPC-N2	$R^2_{lab} = 0.94-0.99^a$	$CV_{Rt} = 4.2-16\%^a$	NA	$\delta_{PC} \approx 30$, estimated from Sousan et al., (2016a).	$\eta_d = 0.83-1.01^a$	NA	NA
Dylos models 1100 Pro and 1700	$R^2_{lab} = 0.97-0.99^b$ $R^2_{lab} = 0.64-0.95^c$ $R^2_{lab} = 0.91-0.98^d$ $R^2_{fld} = 0.81-0.99^b$ $R^2_{fld} = 0.58-0.99^e$ $R^2_{fld} = 0.70-0.90^f$ $R^2_{fld} = 0.48-0.78^g$ $R^2_{fld} = 0.40-0.45^h$ $R^2_{fld} = 0.74-0.84^i$ $R^2_{fld} = 0.55^j$	$CV_{Rt} = 1.4-8.0\%^d$ $R^2 = 0.67-0.98^h$ $nRMSE = 13.4-46.1\%^c$	$< 1^b$	$\delta_{PC} \leq 20$, estimated from Sousan et al., (2016b). $\delta_{PC} \leq 3$, estimated from Northcross et al., (2013). Did not seem to affect the sensor output under ambient conditions l .	$\eta_d = 0.6-1.1$, estimated from Sousan et al., (2016b). $\eta_d = 0.25-4.0$, estimated from Han et al., (2016).	$\eta_d = 0.5-4.8$, estimated from Han et al., (2016). Slight correlation between sensor output and humidity ($R^2 = 0.18$) l . Seems affected by humidity h .	NA No correlation between sensor output and temperature ($R^2 = 0.03$) l . Sensor response probably not dependent on temperature h .
Plantower PMS 1003	$R^2_{fld} = 0.82-0.93^k$ $R^2_{lab} = 0.69-0.99^k$	$R^2 = 0.99^k$	0.721-10.5 k	NA	NA	Slight correlation between sensor output and humidity ($R^2 = 0.09-0.17$) k .	No correlation between sensor output and temperature ($R^2 < 0.02$) k .
Plantower PMS 3003	$R^2_{lab} = 0.73-0.97^k$	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Samyoung DSM501A	$R^2_{lab} = 0.88-0.90^l$ $R^2_{lab} \approx 0.50^m$ $R^2_{lab} = 0.58-0.97^c$ $R^2_{fld} = 0.07-0.46^t$	$CV_{Rt} = 2-28\%^l$ $nRMSE = 22.3-52.7\%^c$	4.28-11.4 l 10 t	$\delta_{PC} \leq 8$, estimated from Wang et al., (2015).	$\delta_{PS} \leq 18$, estimated from Wang et al., (2015).	$\delta_{RH-PM} \leq 2.8$, estimated from Wang et al., (2015).	$\delta_{T-PM} \leq 1.2$, estimated from Wang et al., (2015).
Sharp DN7C3CA006	$R^2_{lab} = 0.98-0.99^d$	$CV_{Rt} = 0.8-7.1\%^d$	NA	$\delta_{PC} \leq 2$, estimated from Sousan et al., (2016b).	NA	NA	NA
Sharp GP2Y1010AU0F	$R^2_{lab} = 0.42-0.99^c$ $R^2_{lab} = 0.95-0.99^d$ $R^2_{lab} = 0.98-0.99^l$ $R^2_{lab} = 0.92-0.98^m$ $R^2_{fld} = 0.72^h$ $R^2_{fld} = 0.99^g$	$CV_{Rt} = 5-25\%^l$ $CV_{Rr} = 0.9-5.9\%^d$ $nRMSE = 2.6-118.2\%^c$	26.1 26.9 l	$\delta_{PC} \leq 6$, estimated from Wang et al., (2015). $\delta_{PC} \leq 4$, estimated from Sousan et al., (2016b).	$\delta_{PS} \leq 2.4$, estimated from Wang et al., (2015).	$\delta_{RH-PM} \leq 1.5$, estimated from Wang et al., (2015).	$\delta_{T-PM} \leq 1.5$, estimated from Wang et al., (2015). Baseline response linearly proportional to temperature o . Seems unaffected by temperature a .
Shinyei PPD42NS	$R^2_{lab} = 0.66-0.99^p$ $R^2_{lab} = 0.93-0.96^l$ $R^2_{fld} < 0.16^h$ $R^2_{fld} = 0.53-0.98^q$ $R^2_{fld} = 0.55-0.94^e$ $R^2_{lab} = 0.50-0.80^k$	$CV_{Rt} = 4-28\%^l$ $R^2 = 0.91-0.94^e$ $R^2 = 0.25-0.44^h$	4.59-6.44 l 1 p	$\delta_{PC} \leq 18$, estimated from Wang et al., (2015).	$\delta_{PS} \leq 24$, estimated from Wang et al., (2015). $\delta_{PS} \leq 13$, estimated from Austin et al., (2015).	$\delta_{RH-PM} \leq 8.0$, estimated from Wang et al., (2015). Seems affected by humidity q . Slight correlation between sensor output and humidity ($R^2 = 0.01-0.27$) e .	$\delta_{T-PM} \leq 1.6$, estimated from Wang et al., (2015). Seems affected by temperature q . No correlation between sensor output and temperature ($R^2 = 0.01$) e .
Shinyei PPD60PV	$R^2_{fld} = 0.43^h$	$R^2 = 0.98-1.0^h$	NA	NA	NA	Seems unaffected by humidity h .	Seems unaffected by temperature h .

R^2 and CV are the coefficients of determination and variance, respectively. The subscript is lab or fld when referring to comparison between sensor and reference measurements under laboratory or field conditions, respectively; subscript is Rt or Rr when referring to repeatability or reproducibility, respectively. nRMSE is the normalised root mean square error, which is define as $nRMSE = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (M_{Ai} - M_{Bi})^2}}{\frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n M_{Ai} + M_{Bi}}$, where M_{Ai} and M_{Bi} are the i^{th} values measured by sensors A and B, respectively, and n is the number of measurements. δ_{PC} , δ_{PS} , δ_{RH-PM} , δ_{T-PM} is the change in sensor response due to change in particle composition, particle size, relative humidity, and temperature, respectively, measured at the same mass concentration. It is defined as $\delta_x = y_{high}/y_{low}$, where the subscript x is PC, PS, RH-PM, and T-PM when refereeing to particle composition, particle size, relative humidity, or temperature, respectively. y_{high} and y_{low} are the different (high and low) sensor responses under different conditions. NA stands for not available. The alphabets refer to the following studies- a: (Sousan et al., 2016a), b: (Northcross et al., 2013), c: (Manikonda et al., 2016), d: (Sousan et al., 2016b), e: (Holstius et al., 2014), f: (Steinle et al., 2015), g: (Han et al., 2016), h: (Jiao et al., 2016), i: (Jovašević-Stojanović et al., 2015), j: (Williams et al., 2014a), k: (Kelly et al., 2017), l: (Wang et al., 2015), m: (Alvarado et al., 2015), n: (Olivares and Edwards 2015), o: (Olivares et al., 2012), p: (Austin et al., 2015), q: (Gao et al., 2015), and r: (Zikova et al., 2016).

Table 4: Performance characteristics of low-cost O₃ sensors

Model (sensor type)	Comparison with reference measurements	Response time (t ₉₀ , t _{lag} , and t _{rise} in min)	Repeatability (SD in ppb)	LOD (ppb)	Cross sensitivity (in ppb of O ₃ /ppm for CO ₂ and ppb of O ₃ /ppb for other gases, unless otherwise mentioned)	Effect of humidity on sensor output (δ _{RH} in ppb/ %RH)	Effect of temperature on sensor output (δ _T in ppb/°C)	Stability (δ _{time} in ppb/day)
Aeroqual SM50 (MOS)	R ² _{fld} = 0.82–0.94 ^a R ² _{lab} = 0.77–0.94 ^b	NA	NA	NA	NA	Seems unaffected by humidity. ^a	Seems unaffected by temperature ^a .	Seems unaffected by usage duration ^a . Seems affected by usage duration ^b .
UnitecSens 3000 (MOS)	Res _{lab} < 2.0 ppb ^c	t ₉₀ = 52 ^c	3.3 ^c	2.3 ^c	0.015 to NO ₂ , -0.061 to NO, 2.3×10 ⁻³ to CO, -0.076 to CO ₂ , and -1.1×10 ⁻³ to NH ₃ ^c .	δ _{RH} = -0.65 ^c	δ _T = -3.86 ^c	δ _{time} = 0.070 ^c
SGX MICS OZ-47 (MOS)	Res _{lab} < 3.1 ppb ^c R ² _{fld} = 0.77 ^d	t ₉₀ = 9.8 ^c	2.0 ^c	1.5 ^c	0.014 to NO ₂ , -1.9×10 ⁻³ to NO, -7.9×10 ⁻⁴ to CO, 2.2×10 ⁻³ to CO ₂ , and 8.0×10 ⁻⁴ to NH ₃ ^c .	δ _{RH} = -0.02 ^c	δ _T = -0.7 ^c	δ _{time} = 0.081 ^c
SGX MICS 2610 (MOS)	Res _{lab} < 13.3 ppb ^c R ² _{fld} = 0.12 ^d	t ₉₀ = 4.4 ^c	0.2 ^c	0.5 ^c	0.081 to NO ₂ , 0.016 to NO, 3.5×10 ⁻⁴ to CO, 1.9×10 ⁻³ to CO ₂ , and -1.0×10 ⁻³ to NH ₃ ^c .	δ _{RH} = -0.84 ^c	δ _T = 3.1 ^c	δ _{time} = 0.009 ^c
SGX MICS 2611 (MOS)	R ² _{lab} = 0.88–0.95 ^e RMSE _{fld} = 4.2–15.4 ppb ¹	t _{lag} = 1–3 ^e t _{rise} = 5–8 ^e	6.5–46.2 ^e	5.1–11.7 ^e	Response equivalent to 0 ppb O ₃ at >200 ppb of SO ₂ ^e .	NA	NA	NA
FIS SP-61 (MOS)	Res _{lab} < 4.2 ppb ^c	t ₉₀ = 89 ^c	19.8 ^c	n.a	0.024 to NO ₂ , 0.13 to NO, 9.9×10 ⁻⁴ to CO, -1.2×10 ⁻³ to CO ₂ , and 3.0×10 ⁻³ to NH ₃ ^c .	δ _{RH} = -0.46 ^c	δ _T = -2.3 ^c	δ _{time} = -0.007 ^c
AGT Environmental Sensor (MOS)	R ² _{lab} > 0.98 ^e	t _{lag} = 1 ^e t _{rise} = 3–6 ^e	2.6–13.6 ^e	15–23.4 ^e	Response equivalent to 7.5 ppb O ₃ at >200 ppb of SO ₂ ^e .	NA	NA	NA
Dynamo Sensor (MOS)	R ² _{lab} > 0.97 ^e	t _{lag} = 1 ^e t _{rise} = 2–5 ^e	3.3–7 ^e	15–17.6 ^e	Response equivalent to 2.9 ppb and 15.6 ppb of O ₃ at >200 ppb of SO ₂ and NO ₂ , respectively ^e .	NA	NA	NA
Aeroqual S500 (MOS)	R ² _{fld} = 0.91 ^f	NA	NA	NA	Seems unaffected by ambient gaseous species ^f .	Seems unaffected by humidity ^f .	Seems unaffected by temperature ^f .	NA
Alphasense O3B4 (EC)	R ² _{lab} > 0.99 ^g R ² _{fld} = 0.02 ^h R ² _{fld} = 0.13–0.70 ^d	t ₉₀ = 1.4 ^g	0.4 ^g	6.8 ^g	0.92 to NO ₂ , -0.042 to NO, -6.6×10 ⁻⁵ to CO, 2×10 ⁻⁴ to CO ₂ , and 2.5×10 ⁻⁴ to NH ₃ ^g . No cross-sensitivity to NO and CO ¹ .	δ _{RH} = 0.40 ^g	δ _T = 0 ^g	δ _{time} < 0.016 ^g
Citytech O3_3EIF (EC)	R ² _{lab} > 0.99 ^g R ² _{fld} = 0.84–0.88 ^h	t ₉₀ = 1.80 ^g	0.6 ^g	2.7 ^g	0.76 to NO ₂ , -0.011 to NO, 7.0×10 ⁻⁵ to CO, 3.5×10 ⁻³ to CO ₂ , and 1.6×10 ⁻³ to NH ₃ ^g .	δ _{RH} = -0.022 ^g . Seems unaffected by humidity ^h .	δ _T = 1.3 ^g . Seems unaffected by temperature ^h .	δ _{time} < 0.142 ^h . Seems affected by usage duration ^h .
Alphasense OX-B421 (EC)	R ² _{lab} = 0.99 ¹ R ² _{fld} = 0.01–0.66 ⁱ	NA	1.9 ¹	1.8 ¹	1.0 to NO ₂ , -0.251 to NO, 0 to CO, 0.22 to CO ₂ , and -0.036 to SO ₂ , estimated from Lewis et al., (2016). No cross-sensitivity to NO and CO ¹ .	1.28, estimated from Lewis et al., (2016).	NA	NA
Aeroqual S300 (MOS)	SE _{lab} = 3–8 ppb ^j SE _{fld} = 5 ppb ^j SE _{fld} = 6 ppb ^k	NA	NA	NA	Unaffected by ambient NO ^k .	Slightly affected by humidity ^k .	NA	δ _{time} < 0.06 ^j . Stable response for 4 months ^j . Significant sensor drift within 2 months ^l .

R² is the coefficient of determination, Res the residual (sensor measured value minus reference value), SE the standard error, RMSE the room mean squared error, t₉₀ the mean of t₀₋₉₀ (the time needed for a sensor to reach 90% of the final stable value) and t₉₀₋₀ (the time needed by a sensor to reach zero concentration) t_{lag} the time interval between a step change in input concentration and the first observable corresponding change in measurement response, t_{rise} the time interval between the initial measurement response and 95% of final response after a step increase in input concentration, SD the standard deviation of repeated measurements, δ_{RH} the change in sensor response in ppb per percentage point increase in relative humidity, δ_T the change in sensor response in ppb per °C increase in temperature, and δ_{time} the change in sensor response in ppb per day. The subscript is lab or fld when referring to comparison between sensor and reference measurements under laboratory or field conditions, respectively. MOS stands for metal-oxide-semiconductor sensor, EC for electrochemical sensor, LOD for limit of detection, RH for relative humidity, and NA for not available. The alphabets refer to the following studies: a: (Jiao et al., 2016), b: (Molchanov et al., 2015), c: (Spinellea et al., 2016), d: (Borrego et al., 2016), e: (Williams et al., 2014c), f: (Lin et al., 2015), g: (Spinelle et al., 2015a), h: (Spinelle et al., 2015b), i: (Castell et al., 2016), j: (Williams et al., 2013), k: (Bart et al., 2014), and l: (Piedrahita et al., 2014).

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5